

D5.3 – Middleware prototype

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIoD	AI on Demand
API	Application Programming Interface
BCA	Bonseyes Community Association
BTFS	BitTorrent File System
BTH	Blekinge Institute of Technology
BTT	BitTorrent Token
BTTC	BitTorrent Chain
CETIC	Centre of Excellence in Information and Communication Technologies
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DApp	Decentralized Application
DAO	Decentralized Autonomous Organizations
DePIN	Decentralized Incentive Networks
DEVP2P	DevP2P network protocols for Ethereum peer-to-peer
DID	Decentralized Identities
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
ERC-20	Ethereum token standard
ERC-1056	Standard for Decentralized Identities on Ethereum
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol

IoT	Internet of Things
IPFS	InterPlanetary File System
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-RPC	A lightweight remote procedure call protocol
KUL	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
M2M	Machine to Machine
ML	Machine Learning
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PoS	Proof of Stake
PoW	Proof of Work
RF	Functional Requirement
SD	Sequence Diagram
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TEAL	Algorand Smart Contract Language
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TPU	Tensor Processing Unit
Transaction	Refers a blockchain transaction
TRON	Bockchain Network
UEDIN	The University of Edinburgh
USAL	University of Salamanca
VC	Verifiable Credentials
VICOM	Visual Communication and Interaction Technologies Centre
VLab	Virtual Lab
Websocket	TCP Protocol provides simultaneous two-way communication channel

XML

Extensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

In complex environments such as those incorporating distributed and edge computing, middleware plays a critical role in meeting the communication and performance requirements of distributed systems by providing communication flow and integration capabilities. Its inherent advantages, such as abstraction of complexities, enhanced interoperability and scalability, make it ideal for managing tasks such as federated learning in edge AI environments. In addition, by supporting secure and energy-efficient operations, the middleware fosters sustainability, enabling green blockchain solutions and low-power distributed ledger technologies (DLTs) to thrive for managing dynamic ecosystems such as dAIEDGE.

This deliverable D5.3, "Middleware prototype" presents the first version of dAIEDGE middleware. This work has been developed during the first year of dAIEDGE project from M4 to M16. In general, the document outlines the first version of the middleware developed collaboratively with task partners, by the University of Salamanca (USAL) as part of Task T5.2, "Middleware and Networks for Edge AI," within the dAIEDGE project. This task reflects a joint effort involving multiple participants, including BCA, BTH, CETIC, KUL, VICOM, and UEDIN.

Task 5.2 Objectives:

- Map communication requirements with network performance criteria (reliability, delay, delay variation, throughput) and develop novel mapping of edge AI performance requirements and communication layer requirements.
- Developing robust, secure and low-power communication schemes for federated learning while enhancing cloud-native 5G/B5G programmability, orchestration and optimization concepts in the edge computing continuum (cloud to edge).
- Research green DLT based transactions with green blockchain and low-power Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs), as well as green Smart Contract protocols.

Document description:

This document lays the foundations of the middleware developed for the project; by first describing the middleware concept and the scope it will have within the dAIEDGE project (see Section 1).

The second section (2) details the investigation process done to explore all DLT implementation options and documents the functional and non-functional requirements of the middleware.

Section 3 reports the architecture of the middleware, defining the overall middleware architecture, the layered architecture that can be deployed within the nodes.

Section 4 presents how the middleware integrates with the project use cases described in WP6 also talks about the integration with third parties.

Finally, in section 5, we present the details of the implementation with the explanation of the Smart Contracts developed and the source code.

Annexes A and B include the references used for research and sequence diagrams representing the use cases in which the blockchain is used.

Stakeholder Contributions:

- **USAL (Task Leader):** Leads the task with the requirement elicitation and analysis, network performance criteria and the edge computing. Also, research's int DLT and 4th generation blockchain-based transaction certification and auditing mechanisms relying on Smart Contracts, for all communications.
- **BCA:** Contributed to eliciting the requirements for DLT based transactions to be implemented in the AI Virtual Lab and Bonseyes Marketplace.
- **BTH:** Assisted with Blockchain-based marketplaces as well as on designing 5G/B5G networking service for distributed AI at the edge.
- **CETIC:** Provides DMWay to facilitate data sharing for the deployment of AI processing and communication between decentralized AI services.
- **KUL:** Contribute to the development of secure and lightweight security mechanisms for federated learning and green DLT-based transactions.
- **VICOM:** Participate in the middleware development required for deploying Edge AI algorithms related to warehouse and space use cases.
- **UEDIN:** Works on smart AI communication mechanisms and optimized information communication choices for AI learning and adaptation.

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1. Introduction to Middleware concept and scope

The concept of middleware is a broad one that can be applied to a wide range of application environments. In essence, middleware is a bridge layer that sits between different software components, applications or systems, with the aim of facilitating communication.

Middleware is a versatile technology that addresses a range of specific needs within an enterprise or distributed environment. These needs can be as simple as communication and data access, or as complex as transaction management, microservices support, and IoT integration. As distributed systems have evolved, so too has middleware, moving from early monolithic designs to modern cloud-native architecture.

Middleware in dAIEDGE represents the challenge to interconnect some elements developed by some partners. In the Gran Agreement document middleware is defined as the element that provides data communication between edge devices.

Particularly among all the middleware concepts that exist, our development focuses on being a **communication middleware** that allows the sending of requests and asynchronous communication, it will also incorporate **application middleware** features as it will allow management and coordination in distributed systems. It can also be seen from the perspective of **IoT middleware**, as it allows communication with entities that have IoT devices that collect data or use these devices as distributed execution platforms.

The implementation that we are going to address has orchestration capabilities between the network nodes and has as main challenges: security, the heterogeneity of the nodes, and integration with data providers. Another challenge to take into account is not to overload the middleware with functionalities in order not to turn it into the bottleneck of dAIEDGE, but to make it light enough so that it does not represent a latency problem in the network and at the same time robust; taking this into account the rest of the functionality that is not in the middleware will be part of each of the nodes itself.

In contrast to conventional middleware, which is predominantly focused on centralized systems, dAIEDGE employs a hybrid model that integrates communication, application, and IoT middleware capabilities to address the challenges of decentralization and diversity in modern edge-oriented AI environments.

This implementation scope is for the first prototype and could change after feedback from partners when testing this MVP, that is going to allow to define the scope of the middleware functionalities better and will lead to the final result at the end of the activity and will be reflected in deliverable D5.4.

1.1. Methodology

In order to establish a final Middleware design, a clear methodology is needed that covers the stages of research, requirements extraction, design and implementation of the middleware prototype. The

proposed methodology has a series of phases, and several iterations can be made in order to reach the final design:

1. Research Phase:

- Goal: To explore and analyze different DLT technologies to identify the most suitable one for dAIEDGE middleware.
- Methodology:
 - Systematic review of scientific and technical literature on DLT technologies, focusing on aspects such as scalability, security, energy efficiency and suitability for AI applications at the edge.
 - Comparative Analysis: Compare candidate DLT technologies based on predefined criteria such as performance, scalability, security, technology maturity and developer community.
- Results: Detailed report documenting DLT research, including technology comparison, proof-of-concept results and justification for the selected DLT technology.

2. Requirements Identification Phase:

- Goal: Define the functional and non-functional requirements of the middleware based on VLab needs and dAIEDGE use cases.
- Methodology:
 - Meetings with partners who will use the middleware: Both online and face-to-face meetings with partners, which aim to identify needs, use cases and specific middleware requirements.
 - Document Analysis: Both the overall project memory and the requirements of other components that interface with the middleware.
- Results: A requirements specification that describes the functional and non-functional requirements of the middleware, including data flow diagrams and use cases of the project in which it can be used.

3. Design Phase:

- Goal: Design the middleware architecture, including its components, interfaces and communication protocols.
- Methodology:
 - Component Modeling: Use component modeling techniques, such as UML, to represent the middleware architecture and its components. Component diagrams should show the relationships between the different middleware modules and their interfaces.
 - API design: Design the APIs that the middleware will use to communicate with the VLab, edge nodes and other system components. APIs should be RESTful, use open standards and be well documented.
- Results: Middleware architecture, including component diagrams, API specifications and communication protocols.

4. Implementation Phase:

- Goal: To implement a first prototype of the middleware accessible by users and meeting the defined requirements and allowing integration with the rest of the components.
- Methodology:
 - Iterative Development: Using an iterative and agile development approach (Scrum), to implement the middleware.
 - Continuous Testing: Continuous testing phases to ensure code quality and middleware functionality.
- Results: Functional middleware prototype, source code, API documentation and integration test environment.

2. Middleware functional and non-functional requirements

2.1. Research processes to extract requirements

2.1.1. Research on different distributed ledger technologies (DLTs)

In this section, a research process has been conducted on green DLT to identify the most advanced networks in this regard. We have collaborated with BCA and BTH to develop this research and a blockchain network compatible with the Bonseyes Virtual Lab and aligns with the security requirements proposed by BTH.

This state-of-the-art document created for research on these technologies. However, for clarity, a summary of the main technologies has also been included and the conclusions drawn.

Distributed ledger technology (DLT) employs a distributed network of nodes, with each node maintaining a copy of the shared ledger. Transactions are recorded in blocks, which are linked together in a chronological order to form a chain of blocks (in the case of blockchain) or a directed acyclic graph (DAG) structure (in the case of DAG-based DLTs like IOTA). DLT provides an immutable record of all transactions, ensuring that once a transaction is recorded on the ledger, it cannot be altered or deleted. We highlight three key principles of DLT to consider in research and development process:

- a) **Decentralization** is a core principle of DLT. DLT operates on a peer-to-peer network, which means that there is no central authority or intermediary controlling the system. Instead, network participants collectively validate and maintain the ledger, thereby ensuring a distributed and decentralized infrastructure.
- b) The **immutable** nature of the ledger ensures the integrity of the data stored within it. Once a transaction is recorded on the ledger, it becomes part of a permanent and unchangeable historical record. The immutable nature of DLT guarantees the integrity of transactions, providing a transparent and auditable record of all activities.
- c) **Consensus Mechanisms.** DLT employs consensus mechanisms to guarantee the legitimacy of transactions and the sequence in which they are recorded in the ledger. Consensus mechanisms, such as Proof of Work (PoW), Proof of Stake (PoS), or Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) consensus algorithms, facilitate trust and agreement among participants in a DLT network.

The inaugural generation of blockchain technology was primarily concerned with the development of cryptocurrencies and decentralized payment systems. The most prominent example of this generation is Bitcoin, which was launched in 2009. Bitcoin is based on a public and transparent blockchain where transactions are validated by miners through the Proof of Work (PoW) consensus algorithm.

The second generation of blockchain sought to enhance the functionality of cryptocurrencies and investigate potential applications beyond payments. One notable example of this generation is Ethereum, which was launched in 2015. Ethereum introduced smart contracts, which enable the automatic execution of agreements and decentralized applications (dApps) on the blockchain.

Ethereum employs a public blockchain and is renowned for its Turing-complete programming language.

The third generation of blockchain focused on addressing limitations such as scalability and privacy with the goal of developing massively used decentralized applications. A notable example of this generation is EOS, launched in 2018. EOS uses the Delegated Proof of Stake (DPoS) consensus algorithm and is designed to be faster and more scalable than Bitcoin and Ethereum. EOS has also implemented governance features in its platform.

Fourth-generation blockchain (Blockchain 4.0) focuses on integration with other cutting-edge technologies to enable new applications and functionalities. It has been identified three main verticals for Blockchain 4.0 applications:

- Web 3.0 is the vision for the next generation of the internet, aiming to create a more decentralized, user-centric, and secure online environment. Blockchain plays a crucial role in the development of Web 3.0 by providing decentralized protocols and infrastructure. With Web 2.0, centralized authorities control platforms and user data, raising concerns about privacy and cybersecurity threats. Web 3.0 seeks to address these issues by leveraging the decentralized nature of blockchain.
- The Metaverse refers to a virtual reality space where users interact with computer-generated environments and other users. It encompasses various aspects such as social engagement, gaming, work, and networking. Blockchain technology, along with other technologies like AI, IoT, AR/VR, and cloud computing, plays a significant role in constructing and securing the Metaverse.
- Industry 4.0 refers to the integration of advanced technologies such as IoT, AI, robotics, and automation into industrial processes to create intelligent and efficient systems. Blockchain 4.0 plays a crucial role in Industry 4.0 by providing the trust, transparency, and security necessary for data exchange.

2.1.1.1. Technologies extracted from research process

For this project, we are seeking a platform that meets two critical requirements: scalability to handle the vast amount of IoT data generated, and the ability to establish a network of nodes. There are some technologies that could provide these characteristics:

- IOTA (Tangle):
 - Structure: Uses a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) structure called Tangle.
 - Characteristics: Allows feeless transactions, scalability, and is suitable for microtransactions and M2M communications.
 - Real-World Example: CityxChange [1], a smart city project in Europe, uses IOTA to create sustainable and efficient energy infrastructures in various cities, integrating IoT for energy management.
- Hyperledger Fabric:
 - Structure: A permissioned modular blockchain platform.
 - Characteristics: Offers privacy, scalability, and flexibility in managing smart contracts, ideal for IoT enterprise applications.

- Real-World Example: Honeywell [2] has implemented Hyperledger Fabric to create an online marketplace for airplane parts, using IoT to track the authenticity and history of the parts [3].
- Ethereum (PoS):
 - Structure: Public blockchain based on the Proof of Work (PoW) consensus mechanism, migrating towards Proof of Stake (PoS).
 - Characteristics: Supports smart contracts, enabling automation in IoT and M2M, though it faces challenges in scalability and transaction costs.
 - Real-World Example: Currently, the full transition of Ethereum to Ethereum 2.0, with its shift to the Proof of Stake consensus mechanism and the implementation of shard chains, is in progress and has not yet been fully completed. Due to this, finding specific examples of real-world applications that exclusively use Ethereum 2.0 is somewhat challenging.
- Stellar
 - Structure: Blockchain with its own consensus protocol (Stellar Consensus Protocol).
 - Characteristics: Suitable for micropayments and financial transactions, can be useful in IoT applications involving small and frequent transactions.
 - Real-World Example: SatoshiPay [4], a micropayment solution, uses Stellar to facilitate fast and low-cost transactions [5].
- Algorand
 - Structure: Uses a pure Proof of Stake (PoS) consensus mechanism.
 - Characteristics: High transaction speed and instant finality, suitable for IoT applications that require efficiency and speed.
 - Real-World Example: PlanetWatch [6], an environmental monitoring project, uses Algorand to record air quality data collected by IoT sensors, leveraging Algorand's high efficiency and speed.
- Hashgraph:
 - Structure: Hashgraph is a data structure and consensus algorithm that offers an alternative to traditional blockchains. It uses a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) to efficiently record transactions and events, allowing high throughput and fast transaction confirmation.
 - Characteristics: Hashgraph stands out for its high transaction processing speed, security through the use of Proof of Stake (PoS) consensus algorithms, and efficiency in managing the synchronization and order of transactions. It is particularly suitable for applications requiring high speed and security, such as financial systems, identity services, and decentralized applications (dApps).
 - Real-World Example: Hedera Hashgraph [7], a public network based on Hashgraph technology, provides a platform for decentralized applications and services such as micropayments, digital identity, and data logging. A real use case is Hedera's collaboration with the health technology company Everyware [8], which uses Hedera Hashgraph to track the temperature of COVID-19 vaccines during their distribution, ensuring the integrity and efficacy of the vaccines through a transparent and secure supply chain.

2.1.1.2. DLT Recommendation

Considering the analysis of those DLTs and the requirements of the middleware, the choice of technology should be aligned with the following key aspects:

- **Network Performance Criteria:** This includes scalability, transaction speed, and the ability to handle a large volume of data efficiently.
- **Edge AI Performance and Communication Layer Requirements:** The chosen technology should support robust and efficient communication, crucial for Edge AI applications.
- **Robust, Secure, and Low-Power Communication for Federated Learning:** The DLT should facilitate secure data sharing and collaboration while being energy-efficient.
- **Green DLT-Based Transactions:** The focus here is on low-power consumption and environmentally sustainable blockchain solutions.
- **Requirement Elicitation and Analysis:** The technology should be adaptable and capable of evolving with the changing needs of network performance.
- **Research in Green DLT and 4th Generation Blockchain:** The platform should support innovative and sustainable blockchain technologies.

Considering these factors, the most suitable technologies from the provided list would be:

- **IOTA (Tangle):** Its scalability and performance are well-suited for handling a large number of transactions, which is essential for IoT applications. IOTA's focus on feeless transactions and M2M communications aligns well with the need for efficient and cost-effective network performance. Its unique Tangle architecture, while posing some interoperability challenges, offers significant advantages in terms of security and data integrity.
- **Hyperledger Fabric:** Known for its modular architecture, Hyperledger Fabric allows for scalable and high-performance solutions. It stands out in terms of security and privacy, offering controlled network environments with known identities – a crucial aspect for sensitive IoT applications. Its robust privacy capabilities and support for private transactions make it a strong candidate, especially considering the need for secure and low-power communication schemes.
- **Algorand:** With its Pure Proof-of-Stake mechanism, Algorand offers a balance of security, scalability, and performance. Its recent advancements in privacy features and support for confidential transactions align with the requirements for secure IoT applications. Algorand's focus on energy efficiency and low-power consumption makes it a suitable choice for green DLT-based transactions.

Each of these technologies has its strengths and could potentially meet the specific requirements of your platform. The final decision should consider the specific use cases and the desired balance between scalability, security, performance, and sustainability. For instance, if the focus is heavily on energy efficiency and sustainable practices, Algorand might be the preferred choice. If the application demands high scalability and unique data integrity features, IOTA could be more suitable. For environments where controlled access and robust security are paramount, Hyperledger Fabric would be ideal.

2.1.1.3. Conclusions

IOTA stands out for its innovative Tangle mechanism, which differs significantly from traditional blockchain models. This technology not only ensures high scalability, making it ideal for handling large transaction volumes in IoT applications, but it is also highly energy-efficient, eliminating the need for energy-intensive mining processes. However, IOTA faces challenges in data management, particularly in storing and retrieving historical data due to the need for data pruning. Additionally, although IOTA is progressing rapidly, it is still in a development phase, limiting its adoption compared to more established DLTs.

On the other hand, Hyperledger Fabric, primarily designed for enterprise applications, offers significant advantages in terms of privacy and confidentiality through its private channels and modular architecture. Its permissioned nature and customizable consensus mechanisms make it more energy-efficient compared to Proof of Work-based DLTs. However, the complexity of setting up and maintaining a Fabric network can be a barrier, especially for those without technical expertise. Its design is also less suitable for public decentralized applications, which limits its applicability in open-network scenarios.

Algorand, with its Pure Proof of Stake consensus mechanism, represents a significant advancement in energy efficiency, addressing environmental concerns associated with traditional blockchain technologies. It maintains a high degree of decentralization and security, making it a strong candidate for trust-based applications, including decentralized finance. However, the learning curve associated with its smart contract language, TEAL, can be steep, especially when compared to more widely used languages like Solidity. Additionally, TEAL's functional limitations, due to its non-Turing complete nature, may restrict its use in applications requiring more complex smart contract logic.

When considering DLTs for fourth-generation applications focused on environmental sustainability, the balance between technical and functional requirements and green principles is critical. IOTA and Algorand excel in energy efficiency and scalability, making them ideal for projects that prioritize these factors. Hyperledger Fabric, while less suited for decentralized public applications, offers significant benefits in privacy, energy efficiency, and flexibility for enterprise applications.

Furthermore, Ethereum 2.0 should also be considered in this context. Ethereum's shift from Proof of Work (PoW) to Proof of Stake (PoS) in its 2.0 upgrade represents a major move towards greater energy efficiency, addressing one of the primary environmental concerns associated with the original Ethereum blockchain. Ethereum 2.0 aims to maintain the robustness and versatility of Ethereum while drastically reducing its carbon footprint. The upgrade promises improved scalability and security, potentially aligning it with the requirements of advanced, sustainable blockchain applications. Including Ethereum 2.0 in the study could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the landscape of environmentally sustainable DLT options.

2.2. Functional requirements

2.2.1. Middleware Core

- **RF-01:** The system **must** allow AI models to be registered on the blockchain, including details of their existence, owner and version history.
- **RF-02:** The system **must** allow datasets to be registered on the blockchain, including details of their owner and version history.
- **RF-03:** The system **must** allow controlled access to models and data, with options for temporary, indefinite or usage-based access.
- **RF-04:** The system **must** implement a role-based access control mechanism.
- **RF-05:** The platform **must** include a marketplace where models and data can be listed for sale or free access, considering versions, temporality and access terms.
- **RF-06:** The system **must** implement a reward token (ERC20) to incentivize users for actions such as selling, offering models or using the platform.
- **RF-07:** The reward tokens **must** be able to be used within the marketplace to buy models and data.
- **RF-08:** The role system **must** allow access to various functionalities and datasets within the platform.
- **RF-09:** The system **must** support the initial distribution of tokens to users to enable the use of the platform.
- **RF-10:** The system **must** integrate an identity management system based on **ERC-1056**.
- **RF-11:** All smart contracts **must** be pausable to comply with regulations such as the **European Data Act**.
- **RF-12:** The system **must** maintain traceability of all transactions within the platform.

2.2.2. Middleware Connectors

One of the connectors of the middleware is **DMway** platform, from CETIC, that collects data from IoT sensors. They will be responsible for standardizing data from various types of sensors, allowing their processing by our Middleware and potential redirection to the blockchain or other parts of the system. Additionally, the creation of a log of devices that will connect and send data within the system is required.

1. Data Standardization

- **Data Compatibility:** DMway must be able to receive, process, and standardize data from a wide variety of sensors, including but not limited to:
 - Temperature sensors
 - Humidity sensors
 - Motion sensors
 - Light sensors
 - Pressure sensors

- **Data Format:** Standardized data must be converted to a common and understandable format for our Middleware platform. Standard formats could include JSON, XML, or CSV.
 - **Data Transformation:** DMway must provide data transformation capabilities such as unit conversion, value normalization, and data aggregation at predefined time intervals.
2. **Connectivity and Communication**
- **API Interface:** There must be a robust and well-documented API interface so that our Middleware platform can interact with DMway. The API must support CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations for sensor data management.
3. **Device Logging and Monitoring**
- **Device Logging:** DMway must be able to maintain a detailed log of all connected devices, including information such as:
 - Device ID
 - Sensor type
 - Connection timestamp
 - Device status (active/inactive)
 - Last recorded activity
 - **Real-time Monitoring:** It must provide real-time monitoring capabilities to supervise the status and performance of connected devices, with configurable alerts to detect anomalies or failures.
4. **Security and Authentication**
- **Authentication and Authorization:** CETIC DMway must implement authentication and authorization mechanisms to ensure that only authorized devices and users can access and send data.
 - **Data Encryption:** All data transmitted between DMway devices, and our Middleware platform must be encrypted using robust security protocols such as TLS/SSL.

2.2.3. Middleware integration with VLab

Also, in the integration with VLab we defined some aspects that both need to have in mind to ensure the systems interoperability in this enumeration can be seen the VLab requirements that are linked to our middleware.

Considering the functional requirements of the VLab, we propose these approaches for the best integration of both services:

- **Remote Access to Research Infrastructure, Assets, and Resources.** Middleware will allow remote access to models, datasets and computational resources, through the API designed for this purpose.
- **Open API for Seamless Interconnection and Aggregation:** The Middleware API developed complies with the Open API standards. VLab will use it in a transparent mode to interact between distributed components.

- **Strategies for Orchestration and Autosizing Services (Kubernetes-Based):** Although this will not be provided directly by the middleware, we will provide in task T4.3 a functionality connected with Middleware and the VLab to have mechanisms for resource management, model deployment and service scaling.
- **Security Mechanisms Ensuring Data Integrity, Privacy, and Trust:** To ensure compliance with integrity, privacy, and trust, the developed middleware has a role-based system that ensures data integrity and privacy by establishing permission-based data access mechanisms and guarantees trust thanks to the transactions stored in the blockchain.

2.2.4. Middleware Certification Authority

As a certification element, a Decentralized Identity Management (DID) mechanism will be used that allows users to control their own digital identities without relying on centralized authority. This solution is based on blockchain offering a trusted infrastructure for user verification and authorization.

The Ethereum standard ERC-1056 [9] provides a framework for decentralized identity management. Instead of storing credentials in a database, as would be done with centralized entities, DIDs are registered in a Distributed Ledger, which ensures that identities are transparently verifiable. This identity management allows users to control who has access to their data.

A key part of this system is Verifiable Credentials (VCs), which function as verifiable digital credentials associated with a DID. VCs allow users to authenticate themselves without revealing unnecessary information. These credentials are immutable and auditable, allowing for reliability and resistance to fraud and/or tampering. VCs provide systems with decentralized identities with a validation layer. This entire ecosystem allows for the removal of centralized certificate authorities, which eliminates this dependency and helps to comply with privacy and security regulations.

2.3. Non-functional requirements

Furthermore, middleware has other requirements, which are not necessary for its operation but are really important for its maintainability, interoperability and scalability.

2.3.1. Middleware integration with VLab

The non-functional requirements of the middleware are also translated into requirements that the middleware must meet in order to adapt to them:

- **Scalability:** The VLab architecture includes an orchestration and provisioning layer. This layer will allow efficient resource management and dynamic scaling of services as needed. Middleware is scalable in that it is modular and deployable on each infrastructure.
- **Interoperability:** Compatibility with existing research infrastructures, tools and platforms is crucial for smooth integration and efficient operation in diverse environments. Interoperability with external platforms such as AI on Demand (AIoD) is crucial and open APIs will be used to facilitate interconnection.

- **Performance:** Low latency is essential for optimized ML deployment, especially in scenarios that require real-time processing. Middleware will help in performance optimization by facilitating efficient communication between nodes and resource management, especially if we attend to task T4.3 of the project, where we collaborate in the standardized deployment of ML models.
- **Reliability and Fault Tolerance:** Resilience against node failures is critical to ensure continuity of operations and resource availability. The middleware design, with its focus on security and decentralization, will contribute to the reliability of the VLab.
- **Security and Privacy:** The incorporation of encryption mechanisms and privacy controls is critical to protect data. Middleware security, such as role-based access control, data encryption and the use of blockchain technology are used to ensure the integrity of transactions.

2.3.2. Security in DLT middleware

To maintain security in middleware, it is necessary to guarantee the confidentiality, integrity and availability of the data handled within the system. In the context of decentralized platforms, privacy refers not only to preserving the identity of users, but also to maintaining user control over their data without the need to rely on centralized entities, which is known as data governance. There are several mechanisms to guarantee this security, and although it is yet to be defined which one will be used in Middleware, they are exposed as part of the previous research process:

- **Ring Signatures:** a set of cryptographic techniques that provide anonymity and privacy in transactions performed on decentralized platforms. This technique allows a signer of a transaction to be indistinguishable from a group of users, ensuring that the identity of the actual signer cannot be discovered, making it difficult to trace the transaction back to the specific user. Unlike traditional group signatures, ring signatures do not require a centralized management system. In these systems, to avoid incurring excessive computational costs, off-chain computations with on-chain verification are used to reduce these costs.
- **Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs):** are another mechanism that can be used to preserve privacy in decentralized platforms. A ZKP allows one party to prove to another that a claim is true without revealing any additional information beyond the validity of the claim itself. They stand out for their versatility, as in addition to transaction validation, ZKPs can be applied to a variety of scenarios within the platform, including identity verification, access control, and other privacy-preserving applications.

2.3.3. Reward mechanisms

Middleware is important in the retention of users and the promotion of new users utilizing the software for its intended purposes. For this case, it is necessary to have a reward system that can be developed thanks to the smart contracts that will be established between blockchain users. The approach made for this reward system is a three-part approach, acquiring new users through

rewards, rewarding older users of the platform and rewarding user actions such as logging in or uploading models. This approach is described below:

2.3.3.1. New Participants in dAIEDGE

- **Option 1:** Upload an initial model for a token reward.
- **Option 2:** Welcome bonus for registration.
- **Option 3:** Buy models on credit; repay platform with a 25% surplus.
- **Option 4:** Referral links for tokens.
- **Option 5:** Combine multiple options (e.g., 1+2 or 2+4).

2.3.3.2. Initial Network Users

- Free models for early adopters.
- Rewards for publishing free models.
- Bonus tokens for the first users.

2.3.3.3. Loyalty System

- Earn tokens for:
 - Logging in.
 - Selling or buying models.
 - Referrals.
 - Using a secondary token system:
 - Percentage of sales into a communal pool.
 - Daily pool redistribution to active users.

The final decision on the chosen reward system will be taken after the evaluation of the first prototype and the beginning of the integration process of the rest of the external components.

This task implements the entire reward system with token exchange based on ERC-20 [10] which allows the creation of interoperable tokens within the Ethereum ecosystem. This standard is chosen for its transparency, which guarantees that transactions are recorded on the blockchain and the automation it allows, using smart contracts. It also offers flexibility, as it allows customization of the rules for issuing and distributing tokens. Users can simply exchange their rewards in decentralized exchanges and use the tokens in other services. It also enables a decentralized governance model through DAOs (Decentralized Autonomous Organizations), allowing token holders to participate in decisions about the system.

3. Middleware architecture and components

3.1. Middleware Architecture overview

To implement the functional and non-functional requirements defined in the previous section, we have proposed the architecture shown in Figure 1. The figure shows the middleware in the central part, the nodes that interact through it, and other components that extend its functionality, such as data aggregators, marketplaces and data catalogues, as well as the auditing system and the certification authority.

Figure 1 – Overview architecture.

- **Marketplaces and Data Catalogue.** Let's first explain these two concepts.
Marketplace: A marketplace can be understood as a digital platform that facilitates the purchase, sale or exchange of goods and services between users. In the case of dAIEDGE

organizations and companies can share, acquire or sell digital assets, such as datasets, machine learning models, software applications or APIs (Bonseyes AI Marketplace) [11].

Data Catalogue: This is a structured inventory that organizes and describes assets or datasets within an organization or system. It provides metadata about data assets, such as descriptions, sources, formats and accessibility, allowing users to search, understand and use them efficiently.

Once these two concepts are understood, it is possible to understand these two serve as centralized hubs for organizing, discovering, and accessing resources like AI models and datasets (AI-on-Demand) [12].

Although the data in dAIEdge can be stored in each of the nodes of the network so that each organization is sovereign of its information, we count on BCA that has Bonseyes AI Marketplace, although it is not yet ready for integration, but is intended to be accessible soon.

Figure 2 – AI on Demand architecture.

Another important resource to have a Data Catalogue is AI on Demand (AI-on-Demand, s. f.), as can be seen in Figure 2. This layered architecture of the Platform shows how different user profiles can access the platform through different interfaces (web and apps). At the core of this service is the portal, in charge of managing all the services it offers (Data, Computing Resources, Models, Software and others). The references that these elements make to real resources are found in the resource layer.

- **IoT data-providers.** As a task partner, CETIC facilitates the integration of DMWay, a specialized module toolbox for developing IoT data processing architectures.
 - It facilitates the integration of disparate devices and data sources.
 - Helps in the management of semantic data.
 - Establish interconnections between devices and data management systems.

Figure 3 – DMWay technologies compatibility.

DMWay, as seen in Figure 3, also is compatible with different data source formats, data interfaces like MQTT, AMQP, HTTP, Serial, Modbus, CoAP, LoRa(Wan), Modbus, Zwave, BT, OPC/UA , Cayenne and different backends, like MongoDB, InfluxDB, TStorage, Thingsboard, RabbitMQ.

Although in the future all nodes will be able to behave as data providers, DMWay provides us as first integration component and provides IoT data to the middleware.

- **Middleware components:** The rest of the middleware elements are centralized in the API developed and described in Section 5.1.2. 5. The portfolio management system, the reward system and the integration with the various platforms that provide assets for the network have been abstracted in this implementation.
- **Node:** This is each of the members of the network, they can be consumers, producers or prosumers of data, models and other resources. The architecture of what can be deployed in each node is explained in the following section.

3.2. Node Internal Architecture

After presenting the general idea of the architecture we will see the internal complexity of the node, which will have a layered architecture that will allow the interaction with the middleware and the rest of the nodes of the network. The internal architecture of the node can be seen in the Figure 4, and is composed of 5 layers, application, privacy, blockchain, data and high computing power layer.

Figure 4 –Internal layers architecture of a generic node.

3.2.1. Application Layer

The application layer is the entry point for users to the interface of their nodes, allowing them to interact with the resources they will provide to the rest of the network users. It also allows the management of their credentials and transaction history within the network.

It is still a layer in the definition phase, and it remains to be seen how it can be integrated with the VLab to have a single-entry point to the functionalities that can be performed within the node itself.

3.2.2. Privacy Layer

The main function of the privacy layer is to protect the privacy and integrity of data by implementing access control, encryption and identity management mechanisms. To this end, security mechanisms will be implemented, which, although yet to be defined, will have the following natures

- **Role Based Access Control (RBAC)**, this access control model assigns specific permissions to each role and, subsequently, users are assigned to these roles, thus limiting what each user can do within the system. This system will be similar to the roles assigned in Smart Contracts to simplify their nomenclature in the system and avoid duplication. This approach was selected for its simplicity and scalability, since assigning permissions to roles facilitates administration.
- **Data encryption**, a fundamental mechanism for protecting the confidentiality of information, will be implemented both in transit and at rest. At rest it is delegated to the data layer, but in transit TLS type protocols will be chosen.

3.2.3. Blockchain layer

Following the conclusion of the research phase and the selection of Ethereum as the preferred blockchain platform, the next step is to define a first draft of the implementation plan to guide the development process. This layer is of critical importance within the node, as it serves as conduct for external communication. It enables interaction with the middleware and other nodes, facilitating data exchange and overall functionality.

Ethereum is a global open-source platform for decentralized applications. Unlike other blockchains, this one is programmable and allows, in addition to the common features of *blockchain* technology, the deployment of Smart Contracts. When interacting with a distributed network, a client must be used, which is responsible for verifying the transactions of each block, helping to maintain security. In the case of Ethereum, this can be developed in different languages such as Java, Python or Rust, without affecting the communication between them. As there are different clients, in case of failure, the security of the network would still be maintained.

One of the most widespread implementations is Hyperledger Besu [13] which is developed in Java under the Apache 2.0 license, and implements different tools intended for the business environment, such as interaction with public or private networks, compatibility with the Ethereum API (JSON-RPC), ideal for our standardization environment, secure and high-performance transaction processing and even the necessary methods for Proof of Stake (PoS) operation.

On the other hand, one of its main features is the possibility of working both on the mainnet and in any of the test networks such as Goerli [14] or Sepolia [15] (networks that have replaced Rinkeby and Ropsten due to the transition to PoS). In addition, it allows working with different consensus algorithms, both Proof of Work and Proof of Stake, reflecting the changes introduced in "The Merge" update, which phases out the use of PoW in Ethereum.

It is fully compatible with the Ethereum API (JSON-RPC), allowing the use of any library designed to interact with Ethereum nodes. For example, Web3, Truffle or Remix. In addition, it allows any decentralized application to interact with the network.

Finally, one of the points in which Besu stands out from its competitors is in the area of permissioned networks. Besu allows the creation of permissioned blockchains, so that only certain authorized nodes can participate in the network, in addition to being able to restrict its use to selected accounts. In this way, only authorized nodes and users can access the network. In addition, it offers a high degree of privacy, as Besu uses a private transaction manager. This makes it possible to keep transactions private between the parties involved so that other parties cannot access their content.

In terms of architecture, Hyperledger Besu is divided into three major parts: storage, Ethereum core and network protocols. For storage Besu uses databases of the RocksDB key-value type in which it stores the blockchain itself. Some of this data can be the content of each of the blocks, a state of the world (relationship between accounts and addresses), etc.

At the core of Ethereum can be found the Ethereum Virtual machine, the virtual Turing machine that allows the deployment and execution of Smart Contracts. The different consensus algorithms, which allow the nodes of the network to reach an agreement. Among the different consensus algorithms, we can find:

- **Proof of Stake (PoS):** PoS drastically reduces energy consumption by eliminating traditional mining (Proof of Work). It consists of randomly selected validators proposing blocks, and other validators attesting to ensure the security of the network. This model is now the standard for the core network.
- **Proof of Authority:** Consensus algorithms designed for environments where clients maintain a trust relationship are typically used in permissive networks. These algorithms include:
 - **Clique.** used for private or test networks. Its mechanism is a validator that proposes a block, which will be sent to the other validators, and they will add their signature. Once half plus one of the validating nodes have signed the block, it becomes a confirmed block. Allows *forks* in the chain, so not all validated nodes will be included in the main chain.
 - **IBTF 1.0.** Allows high performance by avoiding *forks*. Used in private and permissioned networks. In the event that one third but one of the nodes is corrupt, the network is no longer trusted, so it is used in private or consensual trust environments.
 - **IBTFT 2.0.** Its operation is based on clique, requiring that more than two thirds of the nodes agree to confirm a block. It avoids forks in the chain.

Finally, Besu implements Ethereum's own DEVP2P network protocol, in this case written in Java. Apart from that protocol, also, it implements the JSON-RPC API in both HTTP and WebSockets, allowing remote interaction with the node, as well as a proprietary API in GraphQL.

In Besu, privacy refers to the ability to keep transactions private between the participants involved. Other participants cannot access the content of the transaction or the list of participants. Besu uses a private transaction manager, Orion, to implement privacy, each Besu node that sends or receives private transactions requires an associated Orion node.

Private transactions are passed from the Besu node to the associated Orion node. The Orion node encrypts and distributes directly, i.e., point-to-point, the private transaction to the Orion nodes participating in the transaction.

By default, each participant in a private network uses its own Besu and Orion node. Multi-tenancy allows more than one participant to use the same Besu and Orion node. Nodes can be grouped into privacy groups identified by a unique Orion ID. Orion stores each private transaction by privacy group ID.

Besu nodes maintain the public state of the chain for all other participants and a private state for each privacy group. Private states contain data that is not shared in the globally replicated public state.

Besu implements two types of privacy, the first is an Enterprise Ethereum Alliance (EEA) privacy, where private transactions include privateFor as the recipient and the second Besu-extended privacy, where private transactions include privacyGroupId as the recipient. Both privacy types create privacy groups and store private transactions with their privacy group in Orion.

A contract in one privacy group can read or write to a contract in the same privacy group, read from public state (including public contracts), but cannot access contracts in a different privacy group nor can it access a private contract with a public contract.

Given the features of this Ethereum implementation, thanks to its support for efficient consensus algorithms such as Proof of Authority and Proof of Stake and its flexibility in private and public networks, this is an ideal implementation for a sustainable and reliable solution such as the one we are looking for in dAIEDGE.

3.2.4. Data Layer

This data layer stores the resources that each node wants to share, and serves as a local data catalog of available resources. For this persistence layer to be effective, an implementation that facilitates the use of Hyperledger Besu for transactions is sought.

BTFS, initially a file sharing protocol, has evolved into the development of DePIN (Decentralized Incentive Networks). BTFS is based on IPFS with an additional layer that integrates it with BitTorrent and the TRON network. It uses token rewards to incentivize storage on the network, prioritizing economic growth.

BTFS is recommended for decentralized applications within the TRON network, taking advantage of its infrastructure, economic incentives and adoption. Building private networks or custom dApps without connection to BTTC or TRON is complicated.

IPFS is a set of protocols for organizing and transferring data, based on content addressing and peer-to-peer networks. Kubo, the IPFS implementation in Go, is the one discussed in the paper. It is ideal for dApps that need decentralized storage.

IPFS is presented as a base layer on which custom dApps can be built, while BTFS focuses on integration with the BitTorrent network and the use of BTT. Using BTFS in private networks without connection to BTTC removes its advantages and adds complexity. IPFS offers a more flexible and open solution, although it requires additional development for features such as encryption and access control.

Feature	BTFS	IPFS
Built-in encryption	Yes, implemented through its btfs-go client.	No, no built-in encryption.
Access control	No integrated access control.	No integrated access control.

Support for private networks	Difficult to implement, requires manually disabling links to the public network.	Native implementation for private networks.
Documentation and adoption	Limited, due to its recent launch.	Solid documentation and wide adoption, with more time in the market.
Interoperability	Compatible with the public BitTorrent network and TRON, with greater adoption in this area.	Open source and customizable, facilitating interoperability between systems and platforms.
Ease of customization	No specific tools for easy customization.	Official Docker image allows customization through shell scripts.

BTFS seems a better choice for storage layer development because of the encryption however IPFS is more modular versatile and customizable. The storage option will be chosen after performing the two proofs of concept.

3.2.5. High computing power layer

Like the first layer, it is closely connected to the VLab functionality, since it aims to connect the main computing core of the node to those devices used for benchmarking or other specific types of computations (GPU, TPU, ...). This layer serves to abstract the heterogeneity of these devices and facilitate their discovery inside and outside the infrastructure if they are offered as a computational resource.

This development is still pending to verify its integration with the VLab, to verify its functionality and usability within the node architecture. These layers are also modular, if it were not necessary to deploy it due to the nature of the node, it would not be indispensable.

3.2.6. Architectural connection: Middleware-Virtual Lab

As previously described, the connection between Middleware and the VLab is tight and can be connected through several of the layers that must compose the node. Important for integration purposes are the following:

- **Application Layer.** In this layer, which is the one that the end user sees, they can select the resources that can be used by third parties and that he offers in the common market, he can also manage his identity and role settings, accept and deny transactions and acquire resources from other components of the network. On the interface side of the Virtual Lab the application layer serves the user to interact with the hardware virtually without having to be physically present. This synergy of user interaction makes the requirements similar and therefore integrable.

- **High Computing Power Layer.** On the computation layer side, it seeks to abstract the complexity of communication with devices and facilitate access to them, this is similar to what the VLab does when it allows to identify the devices to be computed by performing the discovery process of these devices.
- **Blockchain Layer.** The blockchain layer is the output to the network of the nodes, and the way the VLab will have to find hardware or other delocalized and distributed ones. Therefore, it is another point of connection between the two elements.

Figure 5 – Virtual Lab connection with middleware.

4. Use cases demonstration

4.1. Connection with VLab

The connection between the middleware and the Virtual Lab is close since this allows among other functionalities to access datasets for benchmarking therefore it interacts with the application, persistence and computation layers and the resources (data, models or hardware) belong to another node in addition the blockchain and privacy and security layers appear.

The integration process is still in early stages as the VLab demo has been presented in the project M12, but this will be worked on in view of the final architecture of the node and its interaction with the middleware.

4.2. Connection with Smart Warehouse Use Case

For this use case, the warehouse where the data is generated has several IoT devices, such as cameras and drones that are responsible for collecting information from the warehouse. When these devices store and anonymize the collected information, it becomes available as a resource that can be stored in the storage layer of the node.

As soon as this asset becomes part of the data catalog, it is accessible through the middleware, and potentially desirable by other nodes in the network. At this point, the asset exchange reflected in Figure 24 would occur.

Figure 6 – Smart Warehouse use case dataset transaction architecture.

4.3. Connection with Space Use Case

Within the space use case, satellite images are analysed on the satellite (directly L0 images or transformed L1) to detect and classify sea ice. Due to satellite constraints (power use, latency,...) the use of the middleware is not suitable to be integrated on the satellite.

However, once images and the sea ice classification are downloaded to earth, the middleware will allow to publish labelled satellite images on the marketplace. These labelled images are worthy for people working and researching on space imagery and the middleware will allow them to access them. At the same time, publishing labelled images open satellite image providers with new possible business use cases.

The use case has defined the following workflow, to be integrated with the middleware during 2025:

1. Images from satellite images will be sent to earth, with the labels generated by the onboarding sea ice detection algorithms output.
2. At earth, these images and labels will be enriched with the output of more powerful algorithms.
3. The images, with the onboarding and earth algorithms labels will be sent to the middleware to be integrated into a satellite image marketplace.
4. External users may access the middleware to use images and outputs for their own purposes, which could range from scientific validation of new detection algorithms to commercial applications of any type.
5. The middleware would allow external users to access and integrate data as if it were all hosted on the same platform, and would also support the cloud-based execution of algorithm hosted on the marketplace over the images.

Figure 7 – Space use case dataset transaction architecture.

4.4. Extension of functionality to third parties

The middleware developed is generic enough to integrate with other nodes that provide data and new clients that want to join the organization as nodes.

5. First prototype implementation

5.1. Smart Contracts

To make a first prototype of middleware implementation we developed an API that allows us to interact with the smart contracts for managing roles, resources, access control, identity, rewards, and interaction with data owners.

5.1.1. RoleManagement Contract

- **Description:** Implements role-based access control compliant with ERC-5982, ERC-165, and ERC-5750. Manages roles, permissions, and access rights.
- **Methods:**
 - `grantRole(bytes32 role, address account)`: Assigns a role to an account (RF-04, RF-08).
 - `revokeRole(bytes32 role, address account)`: Removes a role from an account (RF-04, RF-08).
 - `hasRole(bytes32 role, address account)`: Verifies if an account has a specific role (RF-04, RF-08).
 - `setRolePower(bytes32 role, bytes4 method, bytes memory data)`: Sets permissions for roles to access specific methods in other contracts (RF-08).
 - **Pausable Functionality:** Supports pausing operations when required (RF-11).

5.1.2. ModelRegistry Contract

- **Description:** Handles AI model registration, ownership, and versioning on the blockchain.
- **Methods:**
 - `registerModel(string memory modelHash, string memory metadataURI)`: Registers a new AI model (RF-01, RF-12).
 - `updateModel(uint256 modelId, string memory newModelHash, string memory newMetadataURI)`: Updates an existing model (RF-01).
 - `getModel(uint256 modelId)`: Retrieves details of a specific model (RF-01).
 - **Access Control:** Uses RoleManagement for permission checks (RF-04, RF-08).
 - **Pausable Functionality:** Allows pausing of the contract (RF-11).

5.1.3. DataRegistry Contract

- **Description:** Manages datasets, including registration, ownership, and versioning.
- **Methods:**
 - `registerData(string memory dataHash, string memory metadataURI)`: Registers a new dataset (RF-02, RF-12).

- `updateData(uint256 dataId, string memory newDataHash, string memory newMetadataURI)`: Updates an existing dataset (RF-02).
- `getData(uint256 dataId)`: Retrieves details of a dataset (RF-02).
- **Access Control**: Integrates RoleManagement for permission verification (RF-04, RF-08).
- **Pausable Functionality**: Supports pausing (RF-11).

5.1.4. AccessControl Contract

- **Description**: Manages access to models and datasets, supporting time-based, usage-based, and indefinite access. Uses decentralized identities (DIDs) compliant with ERC-1056.
- **Methods**:
 - `grantAccess(address identity, uint256 resourceId, uint256 expirationTime, uint256 usageLimit)`: Grants access with specific conditions (RF-03, RF-05, RF-10, RF-04, RF-08).
 - `revokeAccess(address identity, uint256 resourceId)`: Revokes access (RF-03, RF-10, RF-04, RF-08).
 - `checkAccess(address identity, uint256 resourceId)`: Verifies access, considering expiration and usage limits (RF-03, RF-10).
 - **Role Management Integration**: Uses roles like "ResourceOwner" and "AccessManager" for permission checks (RF-04, RF-08).
 - **DID Management**: Handles identities via the IdentityManagement contract for flexibility.
 - **Pausable Functionality**: Can pause contract operations (RF-11).

5.1.5. Marketplace Contract

- **Description**: Lists models and datasets for sale or free access, enabling transactions with the reward token.
- **Methods**:
 - `listResource(uint256 resourceId, uint256 price, bool isModel)`: Lists a resource (RF-05, RF-07).
 - `buyResource(uint256 listingId)`: Allows users to purchase listed resources (RF-05, RF-07).
 - `removeListing(uint256 listingId)`: Removes a listing (RF-05).
 - **Access Control**: Verifies permissions with RoleManagement (RF-04, RF-08).
 - **Pausable Functionality**: Supports contract pausing (RF-11).

5.1.6. RewardToken Contract

- **Description:** An ERC20 token for rewards and marketplace transactions.
- **Methods:**
 - Standard ERC20 methods (transfer, balanceOf, etc.) (RF-06, RF-07).
 - mint(address to, uint256 amount): Mints new tokens as rewards (RF-06, RF-09).
 - **Access Control:** Restricts token minting to authorized roles (RF-04, RF-09).
 - **Pausable Functionality:** Includes pause capabilities (RF-11).

5.1.7. RewardManager Contract

- **Description:** Manages reward issuance and token distribution, tracking rewards for actions on-chain and off-chain.
- **Methods:**
 - setRewardRule(bytes32 action, uint256 rewardAmount): Defines reward amounts for specific actions.
 - rewardOnChainAction(address identity, bytes32 action): Issues rewards for on-chain actions.
 - rewardOffChainAction(address identity, bytes32 action): Handles off-chain actions reported by authorized roles.
 - getRewardHistory(address identity): Retrieves a user's reward history.
 - **Integrations:** Works with RewardToken, Marketplace, and other contracts to streamline rewards.

5.1.8. IdentityManagement Contract

- **Description:** Implements decentralized identity (DID) management based on ERC-1056, supporting identity registration, updates, delegation, and attributes.
- **Methods:**
 - identityOwner(address identity): Returns the owner of a DID (RF-10).
 - changeOwner(address identity, address newOwner): Changes the owner of a DID (RF-10).
 - addDelegate(address identity, bytes32 delegateType, address delegate, uint validity): Adds a delegate (RF-10).
 - revokeDelegate(address identity, bytes32 delegateType, address delegate): Revokes a delegate (RF-10).
 - setAttribute(address identity, bytes32 name, bytes memory value, uint validity): Sets an attribute for a DID (RF-10).

- `revokeAttribute(address identity, bytes32 name, bytes memory value)`: Revokes an attribute (RF-10).
- **DID Integration**: Supports delegations and integrates with other contracts like `AccessControl`.
- **Pausable Functionality**: Operations can be paused for compliance (RF-11).

5.2. First Implementation Access

For this first implementation an API has been created to allow interaction with the Smart Contracts developed for them using the [GitHub repository](#) to drive the development process and control the produced versions of this API, here users can report detected bugs or make suggestions for implementation.

Also, a [test environment](#), a sandbox for test API and Smart Contracts, has been deployed so that other users and developers can test the implemented functionalities. This test environment has documentation available for consultation both in Swagger format and as call collections for the Postman (*Postman*, s. f.) program.

6. Conclusions and future work

Several results and conclusions have been drawn from this first prototype, which are presented below and will serve as a starting point for further development of the middleware and to have an implemented version at the end of the task.

1. Exhaustive research process in several avenues, which has helped in the component definition process.
 - First the research on blockchain and DLT to obtain the one that best met GreenDLT's requirements and had enough flexibility to create roles, manage smart contracts and issue rewards, to which BTH has contributed.
 - Second, research on the data layer of the nodes to find the best implementation of distributed storage.
 - Third, the instigation of privacy in DLT and the choice of the best mechanisms for both distributed authentication and transaction privacy, KUL has been of great help.
2. Review, proposal and integration of functional and non-functional requirements, of elements to be integrated and of the middleware itself.
 - Functional and non-functional requirements have been established for the integration with Bonseyes AI Marketplace and with the VLab, a process in which BCA has helped us.
 - Requirements elicitation with DMWay, thanks to CETIC, which has been involved in the integration process.
3. The middleware architecture has been established, with a description of its components, as well as a description of the layered architecture of the node that connects to the network.
4. The information flows to be followed to integrate the middleware within the use cases have been established. VICOM and VERSES have been of great help in this task.
5. A series of Smart Contracts have been developed to manage all the information flows that can occur within the network of excellence composed by dAIEDGE partners.
6. A generic, open and documented API has been created, capable of interacting with all the Smart Contracts developed.

6.1. Future Works

Beyond what has been developed for this first prototype, we must continue to advance in the development of the final prototype. A number of tasks are proposed to be worked on after the submission of this document:

- Share documentation and perform a demo for partners to be interfaced with the middleware, e.g. VLab developers.
- Start integration with DMWay to count as a first use case provider.
- Develop the storage layer so that the first users can easily include the first resources in the market.
- Start the integration with AIoD to have a data catalog that facilitates data discovery for the rest of the partners.

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ANNEX B: Sequence diagrams

SD 1: Registering a new model in ModelRegistry

Figure 8 – SD1 Register New Model in Model Registry.

SD 2: Purchasing a model in the Marketplace

Figure 9 – SD2 Get a model in the Marketplace.

SD 3: Granting access to a dataset via AccessControl

Figure 10 – SD3 Grant access to a dataset.

SD 4: Issuing reward tokens to a user for contributing a model

Figure 11 – SD4 Reward tokens transaction.

SD 5: Assigning a role to a user via RoleManagement

Figure 12 – SD5 Role assignment.

SD 6: Updating identity attributes in IdentityManagement

Figure 13 – SD6 Update of identity attributes.

SD 7: Pausing a contract in compliance with regulations

Figure 14 – SD7 Pause a contract.

SD 8: Registering a dataset in DataRegistry

Figure 15 – SD8 Pause a contract.

SD 9: Using decentralized identities in AccessControl

Figure 16 – SD9 Access control with decentralized identities.

SD 10: Reporting off-chain actions for rewards

Figure 17 – SD10 Action notification rewards.

SD 11: Distribution of initial tokens to new users upon registration

Figure 18 – SD11 First send of tokens on register.

Figure 19 – SD12 Daily login rewards.

Figure 20 – SD13 Reward by feedback.

Figure 21 – SD14 Reward after refer a new user.

Figure 22 – SD15 Reward after the tutorial.

Figure 23 – SD16 Token freeze.

Figure 24 – SD17 Model acquire reward option 3 implemented.

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